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What's new during the first millennium BCE in Greece? Archaeobotanical results from Olynthos and Sikyon

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates agricultural practices during the 1st millennium BCE in Greece. New archaeobotanical data provide fresh insights on the plant economy at the urban centers of Sikyon and Olynthos, dated to the Archaic-Classical period. The results show that the staple economy of Sikyon and Olynthos was based on a broad spectrum. However, the analysis records the presence of taxa such as sesame (*Sesamum indicum*) and pine (*Pinus pinea*) that are usually absent in assemblages from Greece. In order to understand the role and the place of these sites within the ancient Greek world, we draw a wider comparison of the ubiquity of the main economic taxa using available archaeobotanical records, covering the Protogeometric period to the end of the Hellenistic period. This paper gives an overview of plants exploited during the 1st millennium BCE and also focuses on the unusual remains recently recovered.

Keywords: 1st millennium BCE, Greece, Archaeobotany, Polyculture, Sesame

1. Introduction

Archaeobotanical studies focusing primarily on the 1st millennium BCE Aegean are scarce. More than twenty years ago, Kroll (2000) published the first review of plant exploitation during the 1st mill. BCE, where he compared plant assemblages characterising this period to previous ones, highlighting the main differences such as the presence of newcomers or the disappearance of some taxa, and their relationship to socio-political changes. It was particularly interesting to understand plant-based economic activities, traditionally restricted to the Mediterranean triad (cereals, olive and grape). Megaloudi (2006) provides an overview of plant assemblages from the Neolithic to the Hellenistic period; however, comparisons for the 1st millennium BCE were limited due to the scarcity of plant assemblages.

While archaeobotanical assemblages dated to the 1st mill. BCE are still limited (see below), texts provide relevant information on plant uses. Written sources such as the *Regime* by Hippocrates (end 5th-beg. 4th cent. BCE) (Jones 2014), *Idylls* by Theocritus (beg. 3rd cent. BCE) (Trevelyan 2014), and *Enquiry into plants* by Theophrastus (end 4th-beg. 3rd cent. BCE) (Amigues 2003), mention a wide range of plants accessible, edible or with medicinal properties. Indeed, beyond cereals, olive and grape, archaeobotanical analysis provides a long list of taxa among which several may have been part of the ancient Greek cuisine. On one hand, archaeobotanical interpretations are dependent on sampling strategies implemented during

fieldwork to recover plant remains, their state of preservation and the archaeological contexts from which they were retrieved. On the other hand, textual evidence can also be biased, misunderstood or simply reflect local particularities. In consequence, archaeobotanical data and written sources might be regarded as a whole and complement each other in reconstructing plant economy.

More recently, a variety of studies, ranging from regional to site specific, have focused on the 1st millennium (Gkatzogia and Kotjabopoulou, 2019; Ivanova, 2013; Gkatzogia, in preparation; Margaritis, 2007, 2014, 2015, 2017, 2020; Valamoti et al., 2018). The recent excavations at Olynthos and Sikyon add significantly to our understanding of the Classical and Hellenistic periods, especially in the light of recent archaeobotanical investigations. Thus, the aim of this paper is to extend our knowledge of plant exploitation during the first millennium BCE, through extensive archaeobotanical work. Expanding on previous studies, this paper compares the occurrence of selected taxa to determine the role of plants within society, and indirectly tries to reconstruct socio-economic systems and communication networks. By studying the archaeobotanical material from these two sites, this paper focuses on the staple food economy in two urban centres, dated to the 5-4th century BCE.

2. The sites

2.1 Olynthos

Olynthos is located in north-eastern Greece in the Chalkidiki peninsula (Fig. 1). The site lies on lacustrine and terrestrial deposits, on the eastern bank of the Sandanos river (Olyntheos) (Papavassiliou et al., 1983). The area has a semi-arid climate with hot summers and cold winters (Anadranistakis et al. 1971). Today and probably in antiquity, the mean annual temperatures range from 5.2 °C in January to 26.5 °C in July. Mean annual rainfall is 445 mm, with the highest precipitation falling in November and the minimum in August1 (climate-data.org).

The first extensive excavations were conducted by Robinson between 1928 and 1939 (Robinson, 1929). The city was founded in 650 BCE (Archaic period), by inhabitants of Pieria, trying to escape the Macedonian army. It became an important political center during the 5th-4th cent. BCE. However, the sacred wars - opposing the Macedonians and the Chalcidians - led to the razing of Olynthos in 348 BCE by Philip II of Macedon (Ginouves, Akamatis, and Hatzopoulos, 1994) and to the later victory of the Macedonians in 338 BCE. Covering approximately 18 ha, the ancient city expanded on two hills (North and South) and was well structured, following an orthogonal organisation (Hippodamian planning) (Fig. 2). Excavated areas revealed residential quarters, with shops and many 'high class' and 'less impressive' houses (Robinson 1932).

In 2014, a new excavation and research project (Fig. 2) was initiated, with the aim of obtaining as much as information at intra-site level (houses) and of contextualising the place of Olynthos in the region (Nevett et al., 2017, 2020). The well preserved residential units offer the opportunity to investigate household activities, urban economy and social interaction within the peninsula and to a larger extent, in the Aegean region (Nevett et al., 2017, 2020). To this end, an interdisciplinary approach was applied and an extensive sampling strategy for archaeozoology, archaeobotany, phytoliths, geochemistry and micro-morphology was undertaken. The aim of archaeobotanical investigations was to recognise domestic

activities such as plant consumption, processing and storage practices, and reconstruct their spatial organisation in a Classical Greek city (4th cent. BCE).

2.2. Sikyon

The site of Sikyon is located in southern Greece in northeastern Peloponnese (Fig. 1), c. 3 southwest of the Corinthian Gulf (Griffin 1982). During the Archaic and Classical periods, the city extended into the fertile plain, bounded by the Helisson and Asopos rivers (respectively to the northwest and south), while the acropolis was located on the nearby triangular plateau (Griffin 1982). Sikyon's climate is semi-arid with variations from sub-humid to arid throughout the year. Summer is the driest period, whereas fall and winter months show high precipitation with total annual rainfalls of 484 mm (Lolos 2011, 32–33). Within coldest months (December-March) the average temperature ranges between 8 and 11°C, whilst during the warmest months (June- September) the average temperatures is 23 to 28°C.

The first investigations in the area were carried out by the American School of Classical Studies in the early 1900 s (Fossum 1905), followed by further excavations between 1920 s and 50 s and 1980 s (Krystallivotsi, 1991; Orlandos, 1957, 1956; Philadelphus, 1926). More recently, the 'Sikyon Survey Project' offered new insights on human settlement and activity in the region (Fig. 3), from prehistoric times to the early modern era (Lolos 2011, 274–82). In 2015, a new collaborative research and excavation project⁴ started exploring the material culture and the urban development of the site (Frederiksen et al., 2017; Müth and Kissas, in press). Within Archaic times, Sikyon was ruled by the tyrannical family of the Orthagorids that was then replaced by an oligarchy. In 303 BCE, Demetrios Poliorketes, a Macedonian ruler in the Peloponnese, destroyed the classical city located in the coastal plain, and re-founded it on the plateau. Investigations in classical Sikyon are still ongoing; however, excavated areas unearthed part of the street grid, major public and religious spaces, living quarters and workshop areas (Müth and Kissas, in press). The archaeobotanical study aims to detect the range of economic plants, outline the dietary habits, trace agricultural practices and provide information on the socio-economic organization, thereby setting similar research goals to the Olynthos Project, and facilitating comparison between the two sites.

3. Method

At Olynthos, sediment samples were collected during fieldwork seasons between 2014 and 2019, in seventeen trenches, in the areas of both North and South Hills. At Sikyon, sampling was applied between 2017 and 2019, in the fifteen trenches scattered within the limits of the ancient city, dated to the Archaic and Classical period (Tsirtsis, in preparation). However, the Archaic period was only represented by burials. At both sites, a similar sampling strategy was followed and all contexts were sampled (e.g. floors, pits, destruction layers, drains, channels and burial contexts). At Olynthos, the floors of the houses were obtained by 'micro' excavation in small intervals. Samples were processed by mechanical flotation to recover charred plant remains. Heavy and light fractions (flots) were respectively retrieved from the bottom mesh (1 mm) and the fine calibrated mesh (0.3 mm) of the flotation tank and then dried in the shade. The archaeobotanical material resulting from the heavy residues were sorted at the sites⁶ and the light fractions were exported and analysed at the Cyprus Institute, using a Leica EZ4E low-power microscope at magnifications of 8X-35X. Whole seeds and fragments were counted (n).

In order to compare the new results obtained from Sikyon and Olynthos to other first millennium BCE sites (from the Early Iron Age to the Hellenistic period), available archaeobotanical data for this period have been reviewed and compiled (Supplementary table 1). Quantity, ubiquity (number of sites in which a taxon is present) and frequency (ubiquity in percentage) of taxa have been used to analyse plant assemblages.

4. Results

4.1 Plant remains from Olynthos and Sikyon

The present analysis focuses on a total of 621 archaeological samples (Table 1), producing 4123 archaeobotanical remains all preserved by charring. Samples were not very rich, the average density of remains was low, 0.61 and 0.44 for Olynthos and Sikyon respectively.

While wood charcoals were not analysed, attempt was made to record their presence. At Olynthos and Sikyon, they were frequently encountered: they respectively occurred in 55% (S=115) and 75% (S=307) of the analysed samples, but were mostly of small size (<4mm). In general, macrobotanical remains were very damaged, often fragmented or covered by calcareous sediment, limiting their identification. Due to their hardness and heaviness, nutshells and fruit stones were better preserved than grains, and mostly recovered in the heavy fraction.

The main taxa at Olynthos are sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.), deriving however from only a single context, followed by olive (*Olea europaea* L.), wild or weed taxa, crops and fruits. The assemblage of Sikyon (Tsirsti, in preparation) is dominated by the wild/weed taxa, olive and crops, while fruits constitute minor component (Table 2).

Crops include cereals and pulses. Some cereal grains were too badly preserved to be further identified and remained as "Cerealia spp.". Barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) is present at both sites. However, while a few indeterminate grains were recovered at Olynthos, at Sikyon hulled barley (two-row and six-row) was identified in larger amounts. Similarly, free-threshing wheat (*Triticum aestivum/durum*) is attested in the two assemblages. On the other hand, glume wheat - emmer (*Triticum turgidum* subsp. *dicoccum* (Schrank) Tell) and einkorn (*Triticum monococcum* L.) – are present at Olynthos and absent at Sikyon. Grains of common millet (*Panicum miliaceum* L.) were retrieved at Sikyon and may be present on the basis of the tentative identification of a single seed at Olynthos. Lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medik.) and bitter vetch (*Vicia ervilia* (L.) Willd.) are present at both sites, grass pea (*Lathyrus* sp.) is only attested at Olynthos, and pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) and faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) are only present at Sikyon. Several fragments of fruits (including nutshell) could not be identified and would require further studies. Fig achenes (*Ficus carica* L.), grape pips (*Vitis vinifera* L.) and olive stones (*Olea europaea* L.) were recorded on both sites. Besides differential abundance of the wild or weed categories on each site, their composition is also different. At Olynthos, it is dominated by wild grass such as *Phalaris* sp., *Bromus* sp. and *Stipa* sp. and includes various taxa such as Chenopodiaceae, Cyperaceae, small legumes (*Astragalus/Trigonella*, *Melilotus/Trifolium*), *Artemisia* sp., *Euphorbia* sp., and *Heliotropium* sp. At Sikyon, despite a wide range of indeterminate taxa, seeds of Chenopodiaceae (*Chenopodium* sp. and *Chenopodium/Atriplex*) and common purslane (*Portulaca oleracea* L.) are dominant. Wild grasses include *Eragrostis* sp. and *Lolium cf. temulentum*.

Cone bracts of pine (*Pinus pinea* L.) were retrieved in the Classical layers at Sikyon (Fig. 4 and table 2). Most of them were fragmented (Fig. 4a), but some specimens were almost complete (Fig. 4b). Characteristic cutting edges and vascular bundles were sometimes clearly visible (Fig. 4b). While measurements would not be representative due to fragmentation, the thickness of five seeds was recorded, with an average of 1.06 mm.

Numerous sesame seeds (*Sesamum indicum* L.) were recorded at Olynthos (Fig. 5 and Table 2) but from a single sample in trench TT23. They were preserved within compact agglomerated lumps - the largest measuring c. l.2 x w.1.5 x t.1 cm – including empty hulls melted together (Fig. 5). Seed coats are partially preserved but cracked, probably due to carbonisation (Cappers et al. 2016, 875 v.2). The average size of seeds is l.2.47 x w.1.4 x t.0.91 mm (Table 3).

As at other Classical sites in Greece, the archaeobotanical assemblages from Olynthos and Sikyon did not reveal a large amount of plant remains. Nonetheless, the results allow comparisons and provide new insights into the plant economy during this relatively understudied period. The archaeobotanical remains of both sites consist of a diversified crop assemblage, composed of emmer, einkorn and free-threshing wheats, barley, millet, lentil, pea, grass pea, bitter vetch and faba bean. Additionally, various fruits and nuts including fig, grape, pistachio, almond and olive were recovered. These results demonstrate that both sites developed a broad spectrum economy, that can be described as 'a little of everything' (Forbes 1976).

4.2 Olynthos and Sikyon within the first millennium period

The composition of the crop package from Olynthos and Sikyon is consistent with those of other sites dated to the first millennium BCE.

4.2.1 Crops

Whatever the quantity, some taxa are commonly found on sites dated from this period. This is the case of emmer, einkorn, free-threshing wheat, barley, lentil, bitter vetch, faba bean and pea, olive and grape. Barley and free-threshing wheat are the most frequent cereals, occurring in more than 40% of archaeological sites (Fig. 6a). Glume wheats (einkorn and emmer) are also commonly found during the first millennium BCE, in particular emmer (*T. turgidum* subsp. *dicoccum*), whose frequency during the Early Iron Age period is equal to free-threshing wheat. But the occurrence of glume wheats appears much lower during the archaic and classical periods (15–25%).

While thousands of broomcorn seeds (*Panicum miliaceum*) have been recovered in the Early Iron Age occupation of Kastanas (Kroll, 1984), only few grains were retrieved in the Classical levels of the site. However, the presence of this taxon is confirmed by single seed found at Corinth, and enriched by the new discoveries at Sikyon and Olynthos. While the overall frequency of this taxon remains low compared to wheats and barley, it progressively gained in importance.

Pulses recovered at Olynthos and Sikyon are also perfectly consistent with those retrieved on other first millennium sites (Fig. 6b). Bitter vetch, lentil and pea are the most common pulses, identified in more than 20–30% of sites. Lentil seeds are not only frequent, they are also found in large quantities as at EIA Kastanas and Kalapodi, or Hellenistic Krania and Kompoloi (Kroll, 1984, 1993; Margaritis, 2014, 2015). In comparison, grass pea (*Lathyrus* sp.) and faba bean (*Vicia faba*) are less frequent, especially from the

archaic period. But the eight seeds recovered in the Classical occupation of Sikyon likely reflect its economic importance.

4.2.2 Fruits and nuts

A large number of fruits can be associated with the Mediterranean world but the most emblematic (excluding olive, which is discussed in section 5.3), well-represented at Olynthos and Sikyon, are grape (*Vitis vinifera* ssp.) and fig (*Ficus carica*). Grape is attested in more than 70% of the sites (considered here) dated to the first millennium BCE but reaches its maximum frequency during the Hellenistic period (Fig. 7), where it is present in all sites. To evaluate the importance of fig, which contains hundreds of seeds, the frequency is a good alternative. As with grape, the occurrence of fig increases between the EIA (44%) and the Hellenistic period (78%).

With minor importance (and frequency), several nuts occur in the archaeological assemblages (Fig. 8). Nutshell fragments were recovered at Sikyon and Olynthos but they could not be identified. However, at Sikyon, other taxa were identified. Almond (*Amygdalus communis*) is attested in the Classical occupation of the site. While its frequency is low during this period, it tends to increase from the Early Iron Age to the Hellenistic period, where it reaches its maximum value (56%).

The presence of the turpentine tree (*Pistacia terebinthus*) is also evidenced at Sikyon. Interestingly, pistachio remains are rare and seem to be present only in the Archaic and Classical periods. Apart from Sikyon, it has only been found at Azoria, Samos and Poros (Haggis et al., 2011; Kucan, 1995b; Sarpaki, 2019).

Similarly, pine (*Pinus* sp.) is only found at sites dated to the Classical and Hellenistic periods, as shown by seeds recovered at Sikyon, Krania, Messene and Thessaloniki (Mangafa, 1995; Margaritis, 2014; Megaloudi, 2005). Thus, besides the rarity of such a discovery, the pine remains of Sikyon also represent the oldest archaeobotanical remains recovered in the Greece.

4.2.3 Oilseeds and condiments

Taxa presented in the oilseed category were not necessarily exploited for oil. They could have been consumed and used in many ways (raw or mixed with other ingredients, for fibres in the case of flax) but their rich oil content is incontestable. Their differential preservation is a factor that should be taken into account since it may bias our interpretation. Indeed, the strong and lignified nature of olive stones explains why they are more often and better preserved by charring than other taxa like flax or sesame, which tend to explode when exposed to fire, reducing the likelihood of recovery or identification. This might explain why olive is attested in 24% samples from Olynthos, while by comparison, sesame is only represented in one. Obviously, olive (*Olea europaea*) is the most emblematic taxon of the oilseed category, as seen at Sikyon where olive is present in 69% samples. It is attested in 71% of all sites dated to the first millennium BCE (under consideration here) (Fig. 9a). Its frequency increases through time, from 57% during the EIA to 78% during the Hellenistic period. Remains of olive (mostly stones) were retrieved in large quantity at EIA Knossos, at Archaic Samos, at Classical Corinth, and at Hellenistic Krania and Platania (Bookidis et al., 1999; Kucan, 1995a; Livarda, 2012; Margaritis, 2014, 2015).

Comparatively, sesame was only identified (in large quantity) at the Hellenistic sites of Krania (Margaritis, 2014) and Thessaloniki (Mangafa, 1995). Thus, the new discovery of seeds from Olynthos can be considered as the earliest attestation of sesame in Greece.

Fig. 9b shows that the widest range of condiments comes from the Archaic period. This is likely the result of a taphonomic bias since they come from the Heraion of Samos where the material was well preserved by waterlogging. Common purslane (*Portulaca oleracea*) is one of the most frequent taxa recovered on sites of the first millennium BCE. Like the numerous seeds identified in the Classical level of Sikyon, large amounts were also found at Geometric Kastanas and Archaic Samos (Kroll, 1984; Kucan, 1995a, b). Surprisingly, purslane is absent from Hellenistic sites.

5. Discussion

The study of plant material from Olynthos and Sikyon shows plant assemblages similar to others of the first millennium BCE. Crops are characterised by the predominance of barley and free-threshing wheat, lentil, bitter vetch and pea. At both sites, cereals are mostly represented by grains, while chaff remains are absent, except for a single glume base retrieved at Olynthos. The scarcity or absence of barley and free-threshing wheat chaff remains compared to grains can be explained by preservation bias and by the ease of dehusking respectively. Rachis of barley are smaller, thinner and more fragile than wheat chaff. Consequently, when exposed to fire, they usually turn to ash and are less often recovered in archaeobotanical assemblages. Moreover, as with free-threshing rachis and glume wheat glume bases, rachis of barley are removed during the fine sieving step of crop processing (Hillman, 1984; Jones, 1983; Wilkinson and Stevens, 2003). After that, hand-sorting can be necessary to clean the products (cereal grains) from small seeds (wild or weeds). In the present cases, while samples come from secondary deposits, the wild or weed category is dominated by small seeds (c. 1–2 mm), including small legumes, *Artemisia* type, *Chenopodiaceae* or *Cyperaceae*, and suggesting the assemblages belong to the final stage of crop processing (before consumption). Additionally, this archaeobotanical analysis shows that fruit cultivation was – as at most sites of the first millennium BCE – mostly oriented toward the exploitation of grape, fig and olive. Their economic importance in Chalcidice (area of Olynthos) can be seen in a text of Xenophon, mentioning large orchards of 360 plethra near Olynthos (Hatzfeld 2006, 5.20.38). Moreover, equipment to process them (pieces of olive crushers, platforms supporting press bed) have been retrieved within the city, highlighting their common use (Cahill, 2002, 226; Nevett et al., 2017, 46).

However, this does not exclude the consumption of other taxa like almond and pistachio, as shown at Sikyon, maybe for specific purposes. Indeed, medicinal properties of almonds were claimed by Hippocrates and later by Diocles of Carystus, who also described its use as food (Albala 2009). The fruit can be consumed unripe, soaked or roasted to

remove the bitter taste, and blanched. The turpentine tree – and in particular its resin – is mentioned in ancient Greek texts, like the *περὶ ὕλης ἰατρικῆς* of Discorides (KI 9.01/10.01 and IM 89.03). Although its fruits are palatable it was widely used for medical purpose (Sarpaki 2001). Similarly, seeds of pine are edible, but additionally the tree produces a resin used for sealing and lining ships and amphorae (Foley et al., 2012; Giesecke, 2014, 127). This might be of interest, considering that the city of Sikyon is located on the Corinth Gulf. Additionally, pinewood can be used to flavour wine (Lardos, Prieto-Garcia, and Heinrich 2011) and this use has been suggested at Olynthos, where pieces of bark were recovered in a pithos (Cahill 2002, 227).

Finally, the diversity of plants consumed during the first millennium BCE can also be reflected by the recovery of common purslane. While the plant can grow wild, historical texts mentioned the use of its stems and leaves in salads (Baumann 1993). Considering the scarcity of wild/weed taxa at Sikyon, one may suggest that the large number of purslane seeds may reflect its consumption.

The general composition of the Olynthos and Sikyon assemblages is also consistent with textual evidence, indicating that a polyculture system ruled the exploitation of the land, combining cereals, pulses, olive and wine production, to reduce risks of famine (Millett 2000, 27). This strategy was particularly important for small farmers (Osborne 2000), as has been suggested for the rural site of Platania and the urban site of Krania, on the basis of the archaeobotanical remains (Margaritis, 2015; 2018). In contrast, the rural site of Kompoloi had a highly specialised monoculture system in vine cultivation and engaged almost exclusively in the production of wine (Margaritis, 2006, 2018; Margaritis and Jones, 2006). Thus, despite the low number of remains, the archaeobotanical composition of assemblages from Sikyon and Olynthos presents similarities with those of Classical urban centers.

Another interesting result provided by this new analysis is the presence of numerous seeds of sesame retrieved at Olynthos. Sesame first appeared in the Indus valley and was likely domesticated during the mid-3rd millennium BCE (Vats, 1997; Charles, 1989; Bedigian, 2000). During the 1st mill. BCE, sesame is attested in the Kingdom of Urartu, at Bastam and Karmir Blur, in modern Iran and Armenia respectively (Hopf and Willerding, 1988; Piotrovskij and Gosudarstvennyj, 1950) but also in the Levant at Deir 'alla, Jordan (Neef 1989). At Karmir Blur, installations for the extraction of oil were also discovered. During the 5th cent. BCE, Xenophon reported the large cultivation of sesame in south-west Anatolia, Cilicia (Bedigian, 2004). In Egypt, sesame is present since the 2nd mill. BCE, as demonstrated by the recovery of uncharred seeds in Tutankhamen's tomb and mentions in the Medical Papyrus (Weiss, 2000; de Vartavan, 1990). While contacts between Greece and Egypt existed since the Bronze Age, they increased during the Archaic period due to Greek colonisation, and were reinforced during the Hellenistic period, when Egypt was under the control of Greeks. During the 1st mill. BCE, sesame seeds, paste and oil are attested in Egypt (Hunt and Edgar, 2000).

Since sesame was used by neighbouring empires during the 2nd mill. BCE, it is not surprising to find it in Greece. Trade, colonisation and wars between Greece and adjacent areas likely favoured and contributed to exchanges or adoption of new products and practices. The plant is mentioned in Minoan and Mycenaean texts – Linear A (su-sa-me) and B (sa-sa-ma) – and may reflect trade between Crete and the Near East (Bennett and Chadwick, 1958; Cline, 1999, 126). As the text from Linear B refers to a merchant account, quantities are indicated in volume and litres. However, it is difficult to say if it was volumes of seeds or oil (Sarpaki 2001).

Despite numerous archaeobotanical studies on Bronze Age sites, sesame seed remains are absent in Greece at that time. The earliest evidence comes from Classical-Hellenistic sites, located in northern Greece where olive cultivation is attested from the Iron Age (Amouretti, 1999; Margaritis, 2007; Valamoti et al., 2018). Classical Greek writers refer only to sesame cultivation abroad (in the Near East). Local environmental conditions, even more in the north, were probably not suitable for sesame cultivation (Bedigian 1985) and it was likely imported, together with other goods. Regarding its importation to Greece and considering that the value of sesame oil increased in the Neo-Assyrian empire due to higher demand (Kennett 1975), sesame was probably considered an 'exotic and luxury' product. Thus, if sesame was known by Greeks since the 2nd mill. BCE, its importance likely increased during the 1st mill. BCE. The

emergence of new elite groups, new interactions and the introduction of different foodways may explain that, even if we should keep in mind that archaeobotanical finds can be biased by the mode of preservation.

At Olynthos, remains of sesame were recovered in trench TT23, which was particularly deep, almost reaching the natural soil associated with a house, located in the southwest part of the southern hill. The discovery of four post holes in the street, against the façade of the house, suggested the existence of a wooden structure. The investigation of TT23 trench was restricted to the northern part, the area of the paved street (Nevett et al., 2020). The archaeobotanical assemblage of sesame derives from a pit, located in that area. The thickness of sediment deposit could have favoured the good preservation of archaeobotanical remains in this context. While this refuse is the single context where sesame was found, one may wonder if its presence was restricted to this house or if it was widely consumed by the inhabitants of the site but was poorly preserved. Does the presence of sesame – which could be considered a luxury product - reflect the social category of people living in this area? Hopefully, further studies will determine the role (function) of the building. While until now it was considered a 'house' (Nevett et al., 2017, 2020), the occurrence of sesame in a 'domestic space' would contrast with other finds. Indeed, as already mentioned above (section 4.2.3), sesame was also identified at Thessaloniki and Krania (building Δ), in both cases public spaces. The former (dated to the Roman period) is a public building destroyed by fire, where many amphorae were stored; in one of them, a pure store of sesame was found (Mangafa 1995). The latter case, dated to the Hellenistic period, has been interpreted as a tavern (*kapeleio*) (Margaritis 2014). Based on this observation, does it mean that sesame was used in particular contexts or for specific purposes? Whatever the answer, it is clear that at this time, sesame remains recovered at Olynthos are the oldest known of the Greek world.

Ancient writers reported the various uses of sesame: the oil was used as means of payment in many places such as Mesopotamia and Egypt (Crawford 1979). It was used for offerings in Old Babylonian ceremonies, for the preparation of unguent in Persia and for lighting purposes in Egypt (Bedigian, 2004; Bedigian and Harlan, 1986; Crawford, 1979). But if in the Near East sesame was commonly used in the form of oil, in Greece, the intensive production of olive oil likely led to the consumption of sesame mostly as seeds (Rawlinson, 1928; Bedigian and Harlan, 1986). Aristophanes and Herodotus mention that sesame was considered fruitful because capsules contain numerous seeds (Henderson, 1998; Rawlinson, 1928). Sesame-cakes were baked for weddings and offered to brides, and sesame-breads were part of feasts for gods.

Sarpaki (2001, 226) also mentioned two methods to extract oil from sesame seeds: by pounding seeds in a mortar or by crushing warm seed in a mill. Whatever the method, the by-product consists of an 'oil cake', used to feed cattle.

At Olynthos, both mills and mortars were recovered, sometimes in the same room (Robinson and Graham, 1938, 208; Nevett et al., 2017, 40). Several buildings show evidence of bread making: some equipment refers to grinding and others indicate baking and cooking activities. Indeed, during earlier fieldwork at Olynthos, numerous saddle-querns and grain mills were recovered in houses (Robinson and Graham 1938, 326–34). One of the houses (A6) contained many grindstones suggesting that the building belonged to a miller (Cahill 2002, 244). Another house (Aviii8), contained mortars and basins, likely used for 'kneading and mixing dough', and vases and bins probably to store the flour, while the presence of ashes and a chimney in another room likely indicates the space where baking was taking place (Cahill 2002, 248). Thus,

it is possible that the processing of sesame seeds took place together with bread making, either to be mixed easily or to share equipment. While at Olynthos several seeds survived by fire, the 'agglomerated' pieces mostly contained empty coats. These remains could result from a preservation bias, but they could reflect the by-product of crushing seeds.

6. Conclusion

Despite the low number of seeds recovered at Olynthos and Sikyon, plant assemblages recovered from these domestic spaces in northern and southern Greece present similarities with other Iron Age, Classical and Hellenistic sites such as Kastanas and Krania. Archaeobotanical results suggest plant economies based on the exploitation of a diversity of crops, including various cereals (barley, glume wheats and free-threshing wheat) and pulses (grass pea, lentil, bitter vetch). Additionally, inhabitants were consuming fruits (fig, grape) and olive. These studies also revealed particularities that could reflect local preferences in foodways or the consumption of 'luxury' products. This is the case of pine at Sikyon or of sesame at Olynthos. Intriguingly, archaeobotanical remains of sesame were found in a relatively restricted area, although this could also be the result of a bias of preservation.

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FIGURES

Fig. 1. Map showing main sites mentioned in the text (Modified from https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Greece_large_topographic_basemap.svg (Public domain Wikimedia Commons). Modern cities are in red while archaeological sites are in black.

a.

b.

c.

Fig. 2. (a) Plan of Olynthos showing the north and south hills and the Robinson's trenches. (b) Plan of the house Bix6, on the North hill. (c) Plan of trench TT23, on the South Hill (Nevett et al., 2017, 2020).

Fig. 3. (top) Satellite view showing the distance of Sikyon from the Corinthian Gulf. Red dots represent the Hellenistic site. Yellow dots correspond to spots where material dated to the Classical period has been found. (bottom) Map showing the location of the Sikyon's plain (made using ArcGis online powered by Esri).

Fig. 4. Cone bracts of *Pinus pinea* (external, internal and transversal views) recovered at Classical Sikyon. a) Fragment of seed with a typical cutting edge and detail of the epiderm with a specific cell pattern; b) Seed almost complete. On the transversal view, the vascular bundles are visible. Pictures were taken with a Hirox microscope HK8700.

Fig. 5. Archaeobotanical remains of sesame (*Sesamum indicum*). a-c) Charred seeds; d-e) Charred seeds partly hulled and e) shows a detail of the coat; f) Agglomerate residue containing hundreds of seeds (front and lateral view). Pictures were taken with a Hirox microscope HK8700.

Fig. 6. Frequency - percentage of sites in which a taxon is present - of cereals (a) and pulses (b). EIA = Iron Age (including the Protogeometric, Geometric). FTW = Free threshing wheat (*Triticum aestivum/durum*).

Fig. 7. Frequency - percentage of sites in which a taxon is present - of selected fruits. EIA=Iron Age (including the Protogeometric, Geometric and Archaic periods).

Fig. 8. Frequency - percentage of sites in which a taxon is present - of selected nuts. EIA = Iron Age (including the Protogeometric, Geometric and Archaic periods).

Fig. 9. Frequency - percentage of sites in which a taxon is present - of oilseeds (a) and condiments (b). EIA = Iron Age (including the Protogeometric, Geometric and Archaic periods). Gold of Pl. = Gold of pleasure.